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Mechanism-resolved operating windows for biochar production from lavender distillation residue

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Abstract

Lavender distillation residue is an underutilized lignocellulosic carbon waste with strong potential for value-added conversion to biochar; however, pyrolysis operating windows are often selected using end-point product metrics alone, with limited mechanistic grounding and weak integration of energy and environmental burdens. Here, a 13-run N_2 pyrolysis design space (200–600 °C; 10–40 °C min⁻¹; 0–30 min hold) was evaluated to develop a mechanism-resolved operating-window framework coupling thermal fingerprints, conversion-dependent kinetics, and decision-oriented screening. Thermogravimetric analysis revealed heating-rate-dependent DTG peak migration ($T_{max} \approx 327 \rightarrow 364$ °C for 5 → 40 °C min⁻¹). DTG overlap was quantified using constrained multi-peak deconvolution with information-criterion selection, showing β -dependent statistical resolvability (two peaks at 5–10 °C min⁻¹; three peaks at 20–40 °C min⁻¹) consistent with overlap-limited separability rather than a literal reaction count. ICTAC-aligned isoconversional kinetics (KAS/FWO/Starink/Friedman) indicated regime evolution: apparent activation energies were comparatively stable through $\alpha = 0.1$ –0.6 but increased sharply at high conversion ($\alpha = 0.9$), consistent with late-stage carbonization where derivative sensitivity increases. Across the matrix, final temperature exerted the dominant first-order control on the yield–carbonization trade-off. To translate mechanistic insight into actionable selection, electricity-normalized indicators and gate-to-gate EF3.0 midpoint burdens were integrated via entropy-weighted TOPSIS, identifying Run 5 as the best-compromise operating point (48.94% yield; 0.85 kWh kg⁻¹ char; 2.05 kWh kg⁻¹ fixed-C). Imposing an FC $\geq 60\%$ constraint shifted the preferred option to Run 4 (61.67% fixed carbon; 8.16 kWh kg⁻¹ fixed-C). Overall, the study provides a reproducible pathway from thermal fingerprinting to kinetic regime diagnosis and energy/LCA-informed operating-window selection, enabling defensible process design for lavender-residue biochar valorization.

Highlights

- Lavender residue was converted into useful biochar through controlled heating.
- Thermal analysis showed how heating conditions affect biochar formation.
- Energy and environmental checks helped select practical production conditions.

Keywords Lavender distillation residue, Pyrolysis, Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/DTG), Isoconversional kinetics, Environmental footprint 3.0 (EF3.0) gate-to-gate life cycle assessment, EWM–TOPSIS (multi-criteria decision analysis)

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1 Introduction

The transition toward a circular bioeconomy is accelerating the valorization of agricultural and agro-industrial residues as secondary resources rather than disposal liabilities (Ravindiran et al. 2024). Among thermochemical conversion routes, pyrolysis is widely applied because it can process diverse biomass streams and generate a carbon-rich solid (biochar), condensable liquids (bio-oil), and non-condensable gases, with product distribution governed primarily by peak temperature, heating rate, and vapor/solid residence time. Biochar is often the most strategically important fraction because of its multifunctionality as a soil amendment, liming agent, long-term carbon-sequestration medium, renewable solid fuel, and versatile adsorbent for environmental pollutant removal (Ravindiran et al. 2024; Enebe et al. 2025; Parvari et al. 2025). However, translating these benefits into deployable systems requires process design supported by mechanistically interpretable and quantitatively auditable links between the heating program, decomposition structure, and conversion-dependent kinetics—rather than relying

solely on end-point product metrics. In this sense, “operating windows” should be defined not only by what the product is, but also by why the product forms under a given thermal history. From a sustainability perspective, this work is particularly relevant to United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and 13 (Climate Action), as it advances renewable biomass utilization, supports responsible residue valorization within a circular-bioeconomy framework, and incorporates energy- and environment-related criteria into process selection.

Lavender (*Lavandula* spp.) is a high-value aromatic crop cultivated for essential oils used in fragrance, food, and medicinal industries. Europe remains a major production region, and global annual production of true lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia* Mill.) essential oil has been estimated at approximately 300–500 tons (Crişan et al. 2023). Because fresh lavender biomass contains only about 0.8–1.3% essential oil, steam distillation inherently generates a substantially larger quantity of residual solid

biomass (distilled straw/stalk material) than the final oil product (Barar and Bensebia 2025). These residues are frequently burned, landfilled, or diverted to low-value composting despite retaining a lignocellulosic framework and residual bioactive fractions (Karagianni et al. 2025). Valorization routes for aromatic-plant distillation residues have begun to emerge, including gasification studies on oregano and lavender residues (Yılmaz Çinçin et al. 2025) and hydrothermal carbonization of distilled lavender stalks (Li et al. 2023a). Nevertheless, systematic assessments that translate lavender-residue thermal conversion data into mechanistically anchored evidence for defining pyrolysis operating windows—and for anticipating carbonization behavior under practical heating programs—remain limited. Published work on lavender and related aromatic residues has often emphasized structural characterization, application screening, or analytical pyrolysis (e.g., Py-GC/MS) (Lesage-Meessen et al. 2018), which is valuable for compositional insight but does not directly provide conversion-resolved kinetic evidence usable for operating-window design, leaving a gap in TGA-grounded interpretation that is explicitly process-relevant.

For biomass residues broadly, severity effects are well established: increasing peak temperature typically decreases char yield while increasing fixed carbon and aromaticity, reflecting progressive devolatilization and carbonization (Atinafu et al. 2025). Studies on other aromatic herbs such as rosemary further show that plant fraction (leaves versus stems) and applied thermal severity can substantially alter biochar physicochemical properties and energy content (Dıra et al. 2024). These macroscopic trends, however, do not resolve kinetic heterogeneity during non-isothermal conversion. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) commonly reveals overlapping regimes, including dehydration, active devolatilization, and a slower high-conversion region associated with char formation, structural rearrangement, and progressive carbonization of the residual solid (Yang et al. 2007). Accordingly, the ICTAC Kinetics Committee recommends model-free (isoconversional) approaches for evaluating conversion-dependent apparent activation energies in complex multi-step thermal decomposition systems, because such methods avoid imposing a single global reaction model on inherently heterogeneous processes (Koga et al. 2023). The Flynn-Wall-Ozawa (FWO) and Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose (KAS) methods are among the most widely applied isoconversional approaches in biomass pyrolysis and frequently provide robust conversion-dependent activation-energy trends across broad conversion ranges (Shrivastava et al. 2025). Model-fitting analyses can provide additional interpretive context; however, ICTAC cautions that single-step

fits can yield biased kinetic triplets when inherently multi-step behavior is compressed into one mechanism and therefore should be interpreted against an isoconversional baseline (Khawam and Flanagan 2006; Koga et al. 2023). A complementary challenge is that strongly overlapped DTG features can mask stage structure, making it difficult to attribute how much of the overall mass-loss trajectory is governed by distinct sub-processes under different heating programs.

A second, often overlooked, limitation concerns how “optimum” biochar conditions are selected. Many studies tune thermal parameters (temperature, heating rate, residence time) and prioritize product-oriented metrics (Koçer and Özçimen 2022; Koçer et al. 2023, 2024, 2020; Özçimen and Ersoy-Meriçboyu 2010), while process energy demand and associated environmental burdens are not included in the decision basis (Desjardins et al. 2024; Gamaralalage et al. 2025). This omission is consequential because increasing severity can improve carbon quality while simultaneously increasing electricity intensity and shifting the overall sustainability profile (e.g., climate-change and resource-use indicators). For value-added processing of carbon waste, selection criteria that ignore energy and environmental burdens risk identifying “optima” that are not deployable at scale. To address this gap, an entropy-weighted TOPSIS (EWM–TOPSIS) framework is introduced here to jointly evaluate biochar performance together with energy- and environment-related indicators, enabling a transparent compromise ranking across competing objectives and strengthening the defensibility of the selected operating condition. Importantly, this approach also allows explicit quality constraints (e.g., minimum fixed carbon) to be tested, rather than implicitly assumed.

Building on these needs, this work advances a mechanism-resolved, data-auditable analysis framework for lavender distillation residues that connects pyrolysis conditions to both product outcomes and conversion-dependent kinetic structure. The framework combines: (i) information-criterion screening of DTG complexity to resolve overlapping decomposition features beyond the moisture domain, (ii) quantitative partitioning of chemical-stage contributions to demonstrate how decomposition structure evolves with the heating program, and (iii) regime-wise interpretation of $E_a(\alpha)$ to identify late-conversion kinetic escalation that is commonly obscured by single-mechanism summaries. By integrating these kinetic insights with a multi-criteria operating-window selection step that explicitly includes energy and environmental decision factors, the study moves beyond condition-based narratives toward transferable, process-relevant evidence for defining pyrolysis operating

windows for lavender residues within circular bioeconomy strategies.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Biomass collection and biochar production

Lavender distillation residue was obtained from a farm in Çanakkale, Türkiye. During harvest at peak flowering, the aerial biomass was cut approximately 5 cm below the inflorescence. Flowers were used for essential-oil production, and the post-distillation solid residue was retained as the feedstock for biochar production and subsequent characterization. The residue was oven-dried at 70 °C for 24 h, homogenized, and stored in sealed containers prior to thermochemical experiments. Biochar was produced using a Protherm tubular furnace equipped with an inert-gas supply and PID temperature control (Honeywell). For each bench-scale pyrolysis run in the tubular furnace, approximately 1.0 g of dried lavender residue was placed in a ceramic crucible and positioned in the reactor hot zone. Prior to heating, the furnace chamber was purged with high-purity N₂ for 15 min to remove residual oxygen. Pyrolysis was then conducted under continuous N₂ flow ($\approx 300 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$) to maintain oxygen-limited conditions and prevent oxidative degradation during heating and cooling. A structured 13-run experimental matrix was implemented to evaluate the effects of temperature (200, 400, 600 °C), heating rate (10, 25, 40 °C min⁻¹), and retention time at peak temperature (0–30 min) on biochar formation. The complete run matrix is visualized in Fig. 1, where individual runs are mapped as heating rate versus retention time within temperature panels and labelled by run number for direct traceability. After reaching the target temperature at the specified heating rate, samples were held isothermally for the assigned retention time (0, 15, or 30 min), after which the furnace was switched off and allowed to cool naturally to room temperature under continuous N₂ flow. Upon cooling, the resulting biochar was recovered and weighed for yield

determination, and the samples were stored in airtight containers for subsequent physicochemical characterization (including fixed carbon determination using ASTM-based proximate analysis, as described in Sect. 2.2).

EWM-TOPSIS was used as a decision-support tool to move beyond single-metric rankings (energy-only or LCIA-only) and to provide a transparent, reproducible compromise selection that simultaneously accounts for product performance (yield and fixed carbon) and burdens (electricity intensity and EF3.0 midpoints) (Behzadian et al. 2012; Chen 2021). Here, electricity intensity refers to the specific electricity consumption (SEC) of the pyrolysis process, expressed as kWh kg⁻¹ biochar and kWh kg⁻¹ fixed C, rather than to the heat content of the biochar itself. The electrical energy input was estimated as an upper-bound from the furnace rated power and the programmed process time (heating plus hold time), and was then normalized on a 1.0 kg dry-feed basis using the measured biochar yield and fixed-carbon content, as detailed in Supplementary File S1. While the EF3.0 categories in this gate-to-gate model show largely parallel variation—so a footprint-minimization ranking can be inferred directly from electricity demand—EWM-TOPSIS adds value by quantifying trade-offs and identifying cases where higher product recovery can offset modest increases in burden, thereby changing the relative order of some runs. The approach therefore complements the direct energy/LCA screening by formalizing multi-objective selection and confirming the best-compromise optimum through a single closeness coefficient C_i (details in Supplementary Files S1 and S2).

2.2 Thermogravimetric analysis and kinetic theory

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out using a TA Instruments SDT Q600 under a high-purity N₂ atmosphere (99.99%, 50 mL min⁻¹) to investigate the thermal decomposition behavior of lavender distillation residue under pyrolytic conditions. For each TGA

Fig. 1 Experimental run matrix for lavender-residue pyrolysis (13 runs)

run, approximately 5 mg of dried lavender biomass was loaded into an alumina crucible for thermal decomposition analysis under controlled non-isothermal conditions. Measurements were conducted under an inert nitrogen atmosphere (50 mL min⁻¹) by heating from ambient temperature to 700 °C at heating rates of 5, 10, 20, and 40 °C min⁻¹. To quantify the kinetic response without imposing a single global reaction model, model-free isoconversional methods were applied to estimate the apparent activation energy as a function of conversion, $E_a(\alpha)$. This approach is aligned with ICTAC recommendations for kinetic analysis of complex solid-state decomposition systems, in which conversion-dependent evaluation is preferred over fitting a single global mechanism to inherently multi-step behavior (Koga et al. 2023). In this study, “ICTAC-aligned” therefore denotes the use of conversion-dependent, model-free kinetic analysis as a diagnostic framework, rather than a claim of a single mechanistic solution. Among these, the Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose (KAS) (Akahira and Sunose 1971; Kissinger 1957), Flynn-Wall-Ozawa (FWO) (Flynn and Wall 1966; Ozawa 1965), Starink (Starink 1996), and Friedman (Friedman 1964) methods were employed. In these methods, the temperature-conversion rate data were used to construct linear plots, and the activation energy (E_a) values were calculated from the slopes of these plots. The equations for the model-free methods used in this study are shown below:

- KAS method:

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T^2}\right) = \ln\ln\left(\frac{AE}{Rg(\alpha)}\right) - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (1)$$

- FWO method:

$$\ln\beta = \ln\ln\left[\frac{AE}{Rg(\alpha)}\right] - 5.331 - 1.052\frac{E}{RT} \quad (2)$$

- Starink method:

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T^{1.92}}\right) = \text{Constant} - 1.0008\frac{E}{RT} \quad (3)$$

- Friedman method:

$$\ln\left(\beta\frac{d\alpha}{dT}\right) = \ln\ln(Af(\alpha)^n) - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (4)$$

In these equations, β , α , and T represent the heating rate (K min⁻¹), conversion rate, and temperature (K), respectively. A , E , and R represent the frequency factor (min⁻¹), apparent activation energy (J mol⁻¹), and universal gas constant (8.314 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹), respectively. $f(\alpha)$ represents the reaction mechanism function, and $g(\alpha)$

represents the integral of $1/f(\alpha)$. The parameter n in the Friedmann equation represents the extent of reaction.

To resolve overlapping devolatilization regimes, DTG rate signals in the 150–500 °C window were deconvolved using a baseline-corrected Gaussian-mixture representation of the non-negative rate magnitude, with $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ candidate peak sets tested (Rego et al. 2019). The preferred peak number was selected quantitatively using residual sum of squares (RSS) together with Akaike and Bayesian information criteria (AIC/BIC), so that peak partitioning was based on both goodness-of-fit and model parsimony (Akaike 2003; Ferfari et al. 2025; Schwarz 1978). Stage contributions were then defined from the analytical area of each retained fitted peak and expressed as normalized fractions of the total fitted area, with fitted components ordered by increasing peak-center temperature (μ) and reported as Stage I–III. In this study, these stage fractions are interpreted as phenomenological contributions to the DTG devolatilization profile rather than as direct one-to-one assignments of discrete elementary chemical reactions. Mechanism screening was supported by the reduced Criado master-plot normalized at $\alpha=0.5$, comparing experimental $(d\alpha/d\theta)/(d\alpha/d\theta)_{\alpha=0.5}$ with theoretical $f(\alpha)/f(0.5)$ curves for candidate models (Gotor et al. 2000). Details of model selection (RSS, AIC, BIC), stage fractions, fitted parameters, stage-boundary definitions, implementation descriptors, experimental master-plot values, model ranking, and experimental–theoretical comparisons are provided in Supplementary File S3 (Tables S5–S8 and S10–S13).

2.3 Characterization of biochar samples

To characterize the lavender residue and biochar after essential oil extraction under determined optimal pyrolysis conditions, FTIR spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and real-time analysis were performed. In addition, the elemental compositions and higher heating values (HHV) of the samples were estimated based on the proximate analysis results. A Bruker Alpha FTIR spectrometer was used to identify surface functional groups in the raw lavender residue and the produced biochars. Spectra were recorded in ATR mode (32 scans) over 4000–500 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. The FTIR profiles were used to assess changes in the lignocellulosic structure after pyrolysis and the emergence or loss of key functional groups. A Zeiss EVO[®] LS 10 scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to examine the surface morphology and structural aspects. Proximate analysis (moisture, volatile matter, ash, and fixed carbon) was conducted using a TA Instruments SDT Q600 thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA) following the thermogravimetric procedure described by García et al.

Fig. 2 Lavender-residue pyrolysis outcomes across the 13-run matrix, showing biochar yield, fixed-carbon content, and electricity intensity

(2012); volatile matter determination was referenced to ASTM E872, and fixed carbon was calculated by difference. The elemental composition and higher heating value (HHV) were calculated using the empirical correlations outlined in Nhuchhen (2016), Poomsawat and Poomsawat (2021), and Parikh et al. (2005), as shown below:

$$C(\%) = -35.9972 + 0.7698VMC + 1.3269FCC + 0.3250AC \tag{5}$$

$$H(\%) = 55.3678 - 0.4830VMC - 0.5319FCC - 0.5600AC \tag{6}$$

$$O(\%) = 223.6805 - 1.7226VMC - 2.2296FCC - 2.2463AC \tag{7}$$

$$N(\%) = 100 - (C + H + O + AC) \tag{8}$$

$$HHV(MJ\ kg^{-1}) = 0.1559VMC + 0.3536FCC - 0.0078AC \tag{9}$$

3 Results and discussion

Figure 2 consolidates biochar yield, fixed-carbon content, and electricity intensity (kWh kg⁻¹ char; kWh kg⁻¹ fixed C) across the explored pyrolysis matrix (200–600 °C;

10–40 °C min⁻¹; 0–30 min). Within the tested range, peak temperature exerted the strongest first-order control on the yield–carbonization trade-off. Increasing the final temperature from 200 to 600 °C at a constant 15 min residence time reduced yield while enriching fixed carbon: at 10 °C min⁻¹, yield decreased from 45.33% to 30.60% while fixed carbon increased from 39.15% to 60.42% (Runs 1–2); at 40 °C min⁻¹, yield decreased from 51.61% to 35.00% while fixed carbon increased from 38.51% to 61.67% (Runs 3–4), consistent with enhanced devolatilization and progressive carbonization under higher thermal severity (Koçer et al. 2023; Lindstrom et al. 2024). Heating-rate effects were condition-dependent, indicating that β influences outcomes primarily through the realized time–temperature pathway rather than acting as a standalone severity descriptor. This is most apparent at 400 °C without holding, where increasing β from 10 to 40 °C min⁻¹ increased yield (30.82%→35.18%) but coincided with a pronounced reduction in fixed carbon (63.64%→22.80%) (Runs 9–10), suggesting that constrained exposure can limit effective carbonization at intermediate setpoints (Fraga et al. 2020; Zhu et al. 2021). Residence time further intensified carbonization under intermediate conditions; extending the hold from 0 to 30 min at 400 °C (10 °C min⁻¹) increased fixed carbon from 63.64% to 67.06% with a minor yield penalty (30.82%→29.30%) (Runs 9 and 11).

Table 1 Gate-to-gate EF 3.0 midpoint results for lavender-residue pyrolysis runs ($n = 13$) based on run-specific electricity demand in openLCA

Run	Climate change (kg CO ₂ -eq)	Resource use, fossils (MJ)	Water use (m ³ depriv.)	Acidification (mol H ⁺ eq)	Photochem. ozone (kg NMVOC eq)
1	0.932101	10.295852	0.639446	0.004372	0.001777
2	2.079302	22.967671	1.426457	0.009754	0.003963
3	0.555676	6.137912	0.381208	0.002607	0.001059
4	0.842476	9.305867	0.577961	0.003952	0.001606
5	0.200760	2.217568	0.137727	0.000942	0.000383
6	0.659641	7.286296	0.452531	0.003094	0.001257
7	1.061161	11.721432	0.727985	0.004978	0.002023
8	1.520042	16.790159	1.042790	0.007130	0.002897
9	1.075501	11.879830	0.737823	0.005045	0.002050
10	0.268875	2.969957	0.184456	0.001261	0.000512
11	1.935902	21.383694	1.328081	0.009081	0.003690
12	1.129276	12.473821	0.774714	0.005297	0.002152
13	0.860401	9.503864	0.590258	0.004036	0.001640

The EF3.0 midpoint results across the 13 runs (Table 1) show a coherent, near-parallel response across the five indicators reported (climate change, fossil resource use, water use, acidification, and photochemical ozone formation). Such co-variation is commonly observed when a shared upstream contributor dominates multiple impact pathways within the defined system boundary, such that operating-condition changes largely scale that contributor rather than shift the hotspot structure. This hotspot-oriented interpretation aligns with LCIA practice, where co-variation patterns are used for decision-relevant interpretation rather than implying independent narratives for each category (Schomberg et al. 2022). In recent biochar LCAs, energy provision during conversion and post-processing has been identified as an important driver of greenhouse-gas emissions and overall environmental performance, supporting this interpretation for the present gate-to-gate mode (Desjardins et al. 2024; Gamaralage et al. 2025).

To integrate experimental performance with electricity intensity and EF3.0 burdens in a single decision framework, an entropy-weighted TOPSIS (EWM-TOPSIS) model was applied to the 13-run matrix using eight criteria: yield and fixed carbon as benefit criteria, and kWh kg⁻¹ fixed C together with five EF3.0 midpoint indicators as cost criteria. Entropy weighting assigns higher importance to criteria that provide greater discrimination across the dataset. In this matrix, yield received the largest weight (0.2396), followed by kWh kg⁻¹ fixed C (0.1385) and fixed carbon (0.0868), while the EF3.0 indicators carried nearly equal weights (≈ 0.107 each) (Table 1). The TOPSIS closeness coefficients (C_i) provide

the integrated run ranking (Table S2): Run 5 achieved the highest score ($C_i = 0.8612$) and was therefore identified as the best-compromise optimum under the selected criteria set, followed by Run 3 ($C_i = 0.8129$) and Run 1 ($C_i = 0.6395$). The lowest-ranked conditions were Run 2 ($C_i = 0.1835$) and Run 11 ($C_i = 0.2133$), reflecting their combined disadvantage across electricity intensity and midpoint burdens within the integrated scoring framework. Because optimum selection is constraint-dependent, a quality-constrained interpretation was also evaluated: when fixed carbon $\geq 60\%$ is required (Runs 2, 4, 9, and 11), the best-compromise optimum within this feasible subset shifted to Run 4 (highest C_i within the constrained set), providing a defensible selection under a high-carbon requirement.

3.1 Characterization of biomass and biochar samples

Figure 3 evidences a pronounced compositional upgrading of lavender biomass to a carbon-enriched biochar after pyrolysis, consistent with the devolatilization-carbonization pathway of lignocellulosic solids. Proximate analysis shows an extensive loss of volatile matter (82.36 \rightarrow 12.73 wt%, -85%) accompanied by a sharp rise in fixed carbon (8.51 \rightarrow 69.63 wt%, +718%), reflecting extensive devolatilization with evolution of gaseous/condensable products (e.g., CO, CO₂, CH₄ and tar vapors) and progressive condensation of the residual solid into a more recalcitrant carbon matrix (Syguła et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2020). The ash fraction nearly doubled (9.13 \rightarrow 17.64 wt%, +93%), as expected from preferential volatilization of organics and consequent concentration of inorganic minerals in the remaining solid (Zhang et al.

Biomass		pyrolysis	Biochar	
Proximate analysis				
Volatile matter (%)	82.36	-85% →	12.73	
Fixed carbon (%)	8.51	+718% →	69.63	
Ash (%)	9.13	+93% →	17.64	
Ultimate analysis				
C (%)	41.67	+73% →	71.93	
H (%)	5.95	-61% →	2.30	
O (%)	42.33	-84% →	6.88	
N (%)	0.93	+34% →	1.25	
Energy				
HHV (MJ kg ⁻¹)	15.78	+68% →	26.47	

Fig. 3 Proximate and ultimate analysis and higher heating value (HHV) of raw lavender biomass and the corresponding biochar

2020). Enhanced aromatic condensation and removal of oxygen-containing functional groups during pyrolysis further support fixed-carbon enrichment and improved structural stability of the char matrix (Li et al. 2023b).

Ultimate analysis corroborates strong deoxygenation and carbon densification: carbon increased from 41.67 to 71.93 wt% (+73%), while hydrogen and oxygen decreased from 5.95 to 2.30 wt% (-61%) and from 42.33 to 6.88 wt% (-84%), respectively. These shifts translate into substantially lower atomic H/C ($\approx 1.71 \rightarrow 0.38$) and O/C ($\approx 0.76 \rightarrow 0.07$) ratios, indicating formation of a more condensed and persistent carbon structure; notably, the product falls within commonly cited stability thresholds ($H/C < 0.4$ and $O/C < 0.2$) for highly carbonized biochars (Oginni and Singh 2020). Nitrogen increased modestly (0.93 \rightarrow 1.25 wt%, +34%), consistent with concentration during mass loss and partial retention/incorporation of thermally stable N-bearing functionalities under oxygen-limited conditions (Li et al. 2023b). These compositional changes are mirrored by the energy metric: HHV increased from 15.78 to 26.47 MJ kg⁻¹ (+68%), consistent with carbon enrichment and substantial oxygen depletion, which reduce the dilution of heating value by oxygenated functionalities and increase energy density on a mass basis (Koçer et al. 2024). Overall, the results confirm that lavender residue pyrolysis yields a low-volatility, carbon-rich solid with elevated ash concentration and markedly improved fuel characteristics.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed to examine the surface morphology and microstructural

evolution of the raw lavender biomass and the corresponding biochar. Representative SEM images are presented in Fig. 4. Figure 4a shows that the original biomass surface was dense and the fibrous structure was partially preserved. No pores were observed and the structure was dense, indicating that the lignocellulose components (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin) in the biomass formed a tightly bound matrix before pyrolysis. In addition, some small surface protrusions were also observed, corresponding to inorganic particles such as calcium or silicon dioxide residues—a typical morphological feature of agricultural residues (Montoya et al. 2017). In contrast, the image of biochar (Fig. 4b) shows that its structure was significantly more porous after pyrolysis. Although the overall cellular structure of the biomass was largely preserved, the cell walls were thinned and even completely collapsed in some areas. This transformation was due to the release of volatile compounds, leaving hollow cell spaces and a stable carbon skeleton. A large number of micropores and mesopores were present on the surface of the biochar, which can be attributed to the pressure difference generated during the escape of the gas phase and tar phase (Cai et al. 2023). This porous morphology is beneficial for adsorption, catalyst support and ion exchange applications (Su et al. 2024).

Figure 5 shows the FTIR spectra of lavender biomass and its biochar. The spectra confirm a marked shift from an oxygenated lignocellulosic matrix toward a more carbonized structure dominated by condensed aromatic domains. In the biomass spectrum, the

Fig. 4 SEM images of **a** waste lavender biomass and **b** biochar produced under optimized pyrolysis conditions

Fig. 5 FTIR spectra of lavender biomass and biochar produced under optimized pyrolysis conditions

broad band at $3400\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to O–H stretching of hydroxyl groups and adsorbed moisture (Permana et al. 2024). The band near 2920 cm^{-1} represents aliphatic C–H stretching, while the peak around 1730 cm^{-1} is associated with carbonyl (C=O) groups in carboxylic acids/esters and related oxygenates (Logeshwari et al. 2024). The region $1600\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ reflects aromatic C=C skeletal vibrations, and bands between

1200 and 1000 cm^{-1} are attributed to C–O–C/C–O stretching typical of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin structures (Tariq et al. 2024).

After pyrolysis, these oxygen- and hydrogen-bearing functionalities weaken substantially. The reduction of the O–H band indicates dehydration and removal of hydroxyl-bearing moieties during carbonization. Similarly, attenuation of the aliphatic C–H band reflects cleavage of long-chain aliphatic structures and volatilization of light hydrocarbons and oxygenates (Sharma et al. 2024). The strong suppression of the carbonyl region ($\sim 1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$) evidences decarboxylation/decarbonylation and loss of oxygenated groups such as carboxyl, ester, and aldehyde functionalities (Chu et al. 2017). In contrast, the aromatic skeletal region becomes relatively more prominent, consistent with progressive condensation and growth of polyaromatic structures during pyrolysis (Zhang et al. 2025). Quantitatively, baseline-corrected band-area integration indicates enhanced aromatization and deoxygenation in the optimized-run biochar. The aromatic skeletal region ($1620\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) increased from 0.100 to 0.193 ($\approx 1.93\times$), while oxygenated functional regions decreased sharply: the carbonyl band ($1750\text{--}1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$) dropped from 0.144 to 0.00174 ($\approx 98.8\%$ reduction), and the C–O band ($1260\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) decreased from 0.151 to 0.0338 ($\approx 78\%$ reduction). The aliphatic C–H region ($2950\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$) also decreased from 0.296 to 0.0336 ($\approx 89\%$ reduction), collectively indicating conversion from oxygenated/aliphatic biomass to a more condensed aromatic carbon matrix consistent with elevated fixed carbon content (Chu et al. 2017; Koçer and Özçimen 2022; Sharma et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2025). Baseline-corrected FTIR peak heights, band areas, and derived indices used for semi-quantitative comparison are summarized in Supplementary File S3 (Tables S1–S3).

3.2 Thermogravimetric analysis of lavender wastes

Figure 6 presents the TG and DTG responses of raw lavender distillation residue measured at $\beta = 5, 10, 20,$ and $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$, confirming the multi-stage thermal decomposition typical of lignocellulosic solids. The initial mass loss below $\sim 100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is attributed to evaporation of free and bound moisture (Agrawal and Chakraborty 2013). The main devolatilization region occurs predominantly within $\sim 200\text{--}400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, where hemicellulose and cellulose decompose rapidly with partial overlap, while lignin contributes more gradually over a broader temperature interval (Yang et al. 2007). Above $\sim 400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the mass-loss rate decreases markedly as char-forming reactions and solid-phase rearrangements become dominant, and the remaining mass at $700\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ corresponds to a thermally stable carbonaceous residue with mineral ash.

Fig. 6 a TG and b DTG curves of lavender biomass at different heating rates (5, 10, 20, and 40 °C min⁻¹).

The DTG maximum shifts systematically with heating rate (T_{\max} = 327, 335, 351, and 364 °C for β = 5, 10, 20, and 40 °C min⁻¹, respectively; Supplementary File S3, Table S4), consistent with finite-rate non-isothermal effects (thermal lag and heat/mass transfer limitations) under faster heating. Directly comparable non-isothermal N_2 -pyrolysis TGA studies reporting T_{\max} values specifically for raw lavender distillation residue are limited. Nevertheless, the present T_{\max} range (327–364 °C) agrees well with the established pyrolytic behavior of lignocellulosic and herbaceous biomass, for which the principal DTG maximum is typically located in the main devolatilization region governed by overlapping hemicellulose and cellulose decomposition, while progressively shifting to higher temperature with increasing heating rate because of thermal lag and heat/mass-transfer limitations (Fraga et al. 2020; Yang et al. 2007). Thus, the systematic upward migration of T_{\max} observed here is consistent with the expected non-isothermal response of biomass feedstocks and supports assignment of these peaks to the dominant devolatilization stage of lavender distillation residue rather than to anomalous thermal behavior. When reported as $d(TG)/dt$, the peak intensity increases strongly with β (DTGmax = 2.211–18.570 % min⁻¹, Table S4); however, after conversion to a temperature basis using $d(TG)/dT = (d(TG)/dt)/\beta$, the peak magnitude remains comparatively similar (0.4379–0.4643 % °C⁻¹; Table S4), indicating that much of the apparent intensification in % min⁻¹ reflects scaling with β rather than a proportional increase per degree. The dominant-peak width is likewise broadly stable (FWHM = 102.66–110.79 °C; Table S4). At high temperature, TG trajectories converge but retain modest differences in residue at 700 °C (18.86–29.31 wt%; Table S4), consistent with the combined influence of heating program and lignin-associated slow decomposition on final solid fraction (Chen et al. 2023; Koçer et al. 2023). A consolidated TG/DTG fingerprint dataset (T_5 , T_{10} , T_{50} , T_{\max} , DTGmax in

% min⁻¹ and % °C⁻¹, FWHM, and residue at 700 °C) is provided in Supplementary File S3 (Table S4).

3.3 Kinetic and mechanism-resolved interpretation

Conversion-dependent activation energies, $E_a(\alpha)$, were determined using four model-free isoconversional methods (KAS, FWO, Starink, and Friedman) (Fig. 7), with complete datasets reported in Supplementary File S3 (Table S9). The variation of E_a with α indicates overlapping steps rather than a single global mechanism. Over α = 0.1–0.6, E_a remains comparatively stable with strong linearity for KAS/FWO/Starink ($R^2 \approx 0.985$ –0.995; Table S9), spanning E_a = 172.912–182.801 kJ mol⁻¹, while Friedman yields E_a = 175.588–191.744 kJ mol⁻¹ and shows greater sensitivity to derivative-signal variability (Table S9). Here, “late-stage kinetics” refers to the high-conversion region of the pyrolysis trajectory, where the more reactive fractions have largely decomposed and the remaining mass loss increasingly reflects carbonization and structural rearrangement of the residual solid. A clear regime change appears at higher conversion: at α = 0.7, E_a increases (KAS/FWO/Starink: 187.446–188.175 kJ mol⁻¹; Friedman: 203.787 kJ mol⁻¹) and Friedman linearity deteriorates (R^2 = 0.732; Table S9). At α = 0.8–0.9, E_a escalates sharply, reaching 260.615–263.335 kJ mol⁻¹ (α = 0.8) and 484.878–498.137 kJ mol⁻¹ (α = 0.9) for KAS/FWO/Starink and 290.822 (α = 0.8) and 504.230 kJ mol⁻¹ (α = 0.9) for Friedman (Table S9); in this regime, rates are low and derivative-based estimates become more sensitive to signal noise and evolving structural/transport constraints (Porcu et al. 2021; Shrivastava et al. 2025; Wang et al. 2018). Average E_a over α = 0.1–0.9 is 223.328 (KAS), 221.922 (FWO), 223.554 (Starink), and 231.061 kJ mol⁻¹ (Friedman) (Table S9). These activation-energy levels are within the range reported for lignocellulosic biomass pyrolysis, although the high-conversion region in the present study shifts toward markedly higher values. For example, non-isothermal isoconversional analysis of sugarcane bagasse reported

Fig. 7 Isoconversional plots for lavender biomass pyrolysis obtained using **a** KAS, **b** FWO, **c** Starink, and **d** Friedman methods

apparent activation energies of 165–180 kJ mol⁻¹ over the 0.1–0.8 conversion range (Aboyade et al. 2013). In the present study, the more stable mid-conversion region ($\alpha=0.1\text{--}0.6$) gave E_a values of 173–183 kJ mol⁻¹ for KAS/FWO/Starink and 176–192 kJ mol⁻¹ for Friedman, which are broadly consistent with that reported range. By contrast, the full-range averages (221.9–231.1 kJ mol⁻¹) are elevated by the sharp E_a increase at $\alpha=0.8\text{--}0.9$, indicating relatively stronger resistance during the late stages of conversion, consistent with progressive carbonization and structural rearrangement.

To quantify DTG peak overlap and assess whether the devolatilization region is more parsimoniously represented by two or three sub-processes, DTG curves were deconvoluted using constrained multi-peak functions and evaluated by RSS together with AIC and BIC (Supplementary File S3, Table S5). Because AIC/BIC penalize added degrees of freedom, lower values indicate a stronger balance between goodness-of-fit and parsimony (Akaike 2003; Caballero and Conesa 2005). Although deconvolution can resolve overlapped thermal events that are not separable by visual inspection, extracted components may remain sensitive to peak family, constraints, and initialization—especially under strong overlap or weakly expressed features—so information-criterion selection was interpreted alongside residual behavior and physically plausible bounds on

peak position and width (Caballero and Conesa 2005; Kim et al. 2022). Figure 8 provides the stage-partition and diagnostic-point framework on a representative TG–DTG profile ($\beta=10\text{ °C min}^{-1}$), visually linking the fixed boundaries in Table S8 to the experimental profiles used in subsequent analyses. Across heating rates, AIC/BIC selection indicates β -dependent statistical resolvability: a two-peak model is retained at $\beta=5$ and 10 °C min^{-1} , whereas a three-peak model is preferred at $\beta=20$ and 40 °C min^{-1} (Table S5).

Stage-resolved peak centers (μ) and normalized fractions (f_i) are summarized in Table S6, and the complete fitted parameter set (A, μ, σ , analytical area, f_i) is reported in Table S7. The deconvolution consistently identifies a dominant mid-temperature contribution ($\mu \approx 312\text{--}338\text{ °C}$; $f_i=0.5005\text{--}0.9480$ depending on β ; Table S6) and, where supported, a smaller high-temperature tail ($\mu \approx 465\text{--}491\text{ °C}$; $f_i=0.0520\text{--}0.1188$; Table S6), where a fitted component contributes negligibly resolved (e.g., $f_i \approx 1.8 \times 10^{-9}$ at $\beta=20\text{ °C min}^{-1}$; Table S6), it is treated as statistically unsupported under the imposed constraints rather than interpreted as a distinct physical stage (Koga et al. 2023). For consistency across downstream diagnostics, fixed stage-boundary temperatures were used for segmentation ($b_1=150\text{ °C}$, $b_2=400\text{ °C}$ for all β), as reported in Supplementary File S3 (Table S8).

Fig. 8 TG–DTG profiles of raw lavender distillation residue under N₂ at 10 °C min⁻¹ showing stage-resolved mass loss; boundaries (150, 400 °C), diagnostic points (T₅%, T₁₀%, T₅₀%), DTG peak (Point A), and residue at 700 °C (Point B) are indicated

Fig. 9 Criado master plot showing experimental mean $Z(\alpha)/Z(0.5)$ (± 1 SD; $\beta = 5\text{--}40$ °C min⁻¹) with A2 best fit and D3 reference; Stage II window shaded

Reaction-mechanism screening was performed using the Criado master-plot framework, in which the experimental reduced-rate function $Z(\alpha)/Z(0.5)$ is compared with theoretical master curves representing idealized

kinetic model families (Criado et al. 1989). Implementation descriptors are reported in Supplementary File S3 (Table S10), and the experimental master-plot values were aggregated across $\beta = 5, 10, 20,$ and 40 °C min⁻¹ and

Fig. 10 Mechanism-resolved composite for lavender-residue pyrolysis across heating rates: **a** ΔBIC stage-count selection, **b** β -dependent stage contributions, **c** isoconversional $E_a(\alpha)$, and **d** integrated mechanism fingerprint summarizing regime-dependent kinetics

reported as mean \pm SD (Table S11). As shown in Fig. 9, the experimental trajectory increases over $\alpha = 0.1$ – 0.9 from 0.1829 ± 0.0560 to 2.7432 ± 0.4712 (Table S11), indicating a strongly α -dependent reduced-rate signature. RMSE ranking identifies A2 as the closest-matching curve within the tested set both over the full α range ($\text{RMSE}_{\text{all}} = 0.2246$) and within the shaded Stage-II screening window ($\text{RMSE}_{\text{stageII}} = 0.1847$) (Table S12), with pointwise experimental–theory comparisons supporting this ranking at representative conversions (Table S13). Accordingly, the master-plot result is interpreted as a shape-consistency indicator within the tested model set, rather than evidence for a single elementary mechanism governing the full lignocellulosic pyrolysis pathway (Vyazovkin et al. 2011).

3.4 Mechanism-resolved analysis composite

Figure 10 integrates four complementary diagnostics—(a) information-criterion stage selection, (b) β -resolved DTG deconvolution fractions, (c) conversion-dependent isoconversional energetics, and (d) Criado master-plot screening—to interpret lavender-residue pyrolysis as a regime-evolving, multi-step pathway rather than a single global event. The underlying datasets are compiled

in Supplementary File S3: Table S5 (RSS/AIC/BIC model selection), Tables S6–S7 (stage fractions and fitted peak parameters), Table S8 (stage-boundary temperatures), Table S9 ($E_a(\alpha)$ from KAS/FWO/Starink/Friedman), and Tables S10–S13 (Criado descriptors, experimental $Z(\alpha)/Z(0.5)$, RMSE ranking, and pointwise experimental–theory comparisons).

As shown in Fig. 10a, information criteria indicate that the devolatilization region is statistically best represented by two peaks at $\beta = 5$ and $10^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ but by three peaks at $\beta = 20$ and $40^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ (Table S5). This is reflected by $\Delta\text{BIC} = \text{BIC}_3 - \text{BIC}_2$ being positive at 5 and $10^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ ($+19.06$ and $+17.00$; favoring the 2-peak model) and negative at 20 and $40^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ (-8.24 and -5.72 ; favoring the 3-peak model). Because AIC and BIC are likelihood-based criteria that explicitly penalize added parameters, differences in these metrics are used to balance fit quality against model parsimony (Akaike 2003; Schwarz 1978). This β -dependence is therefore interpreted as heating-rate-dependent statistical resolvability under the adopted peak family/constraints, not as a literal count of elementary reactions; such fitted “components” in thermal-analysis signal decomposition are generally model-dependent and should be treated as phenomenological descriptors

unless independently validated (Koga et al. 2023; Vyazovkin et al. 2011).

Consistently, Fig. 10b (Tables S6–S7) shows a dominant mid-temperature contribution ($\mu \approx 312\text{--}338\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) plus a smaller high-temperature tail ($\mu \approx 465\text{--}491\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), with an additional low- μ component at higher β whose contribution is either minor ($\beta=40$) or effectively negligible ($\beta=20$). Specifically, at $\beta=5\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ two peaks occur at $\mu=268.13\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($f_i=0.4995$) and $\mu=325.66\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($f_i=0.5005$); at $\beta=10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ two peaks occur at $\mu=312.20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($f_i=0.8812$) and $\mu=474.69\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($f_i=0.1188$). Where three peaks are preferred, the mid-temperature component remains dominant ($\beta=20$: $\mu=325.60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $f_i=0.9480$; $\beta=40$: $\mu=338.49\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $f_i=0.8264$) while the high-temperature tail persists as a smaller fraction ($\beta=20$: $\mu=465.10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $f_i=0.0520$; $\beta=40$: $\mu=491.17\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $f_i=0.0730$). The additional low- μ component is negligible at $\beta=20$ ($\mu=129.26\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $f_i=1.80\times 10^{-9}$) but becomes non-negligible at $\beta=40$ ($\mu=78.36\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $f_i=0.1006$). Because fitted peak count and component prominence can vary with heating program and with the chosen mathematical representation, the “Stage I/II/III” labels in Tables S6–S7 are treated as fitted components ordered by μ rather than fixed mechanistic stages (Koga et al. 2023; Vyazovkin et al. 2011). The energetic diagnostic in Fig. 10c (Table S9) is consistent with this regime evolution: apparent barriers are comparatively stable over $\alpha=0.1\text{--}0.6$ (KAS/FWO/Starink: 172.912–182.801 kJ mol⁻¹; Friedman: 175.588–191.744 kJ mol⁻¹), followed by a high-conversion shift where $E_a(\alpha)$ increases and uncertainty becomes more pronounced—most clearly for Friedman at $\alpha=0.7$ ($R^2=0.732$)—and E_a rises sharply at $\alpha=0.8\text{--}0.9$ (e.g., KAS 263.103→498.054 kJ mol⁻¹; Friedman 290.822→504.230 kJ mol⁻¹), consistent with late-stage carbonization/structural rearrangement where rates are low and derivative-based estimates become more sensitive to experimental noise and baseline/DTG differentiation effects (Friedman 1964; Vyazovkin et al. 2011). The isoconversional methods applied here are standard non-isothermal, model-free approaches widely used for solid-state decomposition kinetics (Akahira and Sunose 1971; Flynn and Wall 1966; Ozawa 1965).

Finally, the mechanism “fingerprint” in Fig. 10d shows that the experimental reduced-rate function $Z(\alpha)/Z(0.5)$ increases monotonically across $\alpha=0.1\text{--}0.9$ (Table S11), and RMSE screening identifies A2 as the closest-matching model family both over the full range (RMSE_{all}=0.2246) and within the Stage-II screening window (RMSE_{stageII}=0.1847) (Table S12), with pointwise comparisons supporting this ranking (Table S13). This master-plot approach follows the Criado reduced-rate formalism developed for discriminating among candidate solid-state kinetic model families by shape comparison (Criado et al. 1989), and the outcome is therefore used as a shape-consistency indicator within the tested

model set rather than as proof of a single global elementary mechanism (Vyazovkin et al. 2011, 2014). Overall, the converging evidence across Fig. 10a–d supports interpreting lavender-residue pyrolysis as a multi-step, regime-evolving pathway: β -dependent resolvability of DTG sub-structure (two vs three components), a dominant mid-temperature devolatilization contribution plus a smaller high-temperature tail, a strong late-conversion escalation in $E_a(\alpha)$, and an A2-consistent reduced-rate signature. Together, these diagnostics support selecting operating windows using explicit decision criteria (e.g., yield/fixed-carbon targets alongside energy/LCA penalties) rather than asserting a single universal “optimum.”

4 Conclusions

This study developed a mechanism-resolved framework for defining pyrolysis operating windows for lavender distillation residue by integrating DTG overlap diagnostics, conversion-dependent isoconversional kinetics, Criado master-plot screening, and energy/LCA-informed multi-criteria selection across a 13-run N₂ pyrolysis matrix. The results show that lavender-residue pyrolysis is a multi-step, regime-evolving process in which the preferred DTG representation depends on heating rate, while E_a remains relatively stable over $\alpha=0.1\text{--}0.6$ and rises sharply at high conversion, consistent with late-stage carbonization and structural rearrangement. Final temperature was the dominant control on the yield–carbonization trade-off. Within the explored design space, entropy-weighted TOPSIS identified Run 5 as the best-compromise condition (48.94% yield, 0.85 kWh kg⁻¹ char, 2.05 kWh kg⁻¹ fixed C), whereas Run 4 was preferred when a fixed-carbon constraint of FC ≥ 60% was applied. A limitation of the present study is that the energy analysis was based on furnace-rated electricity input as an upper-bound proxy and the environmental assessment was restricted to a gate-to-gate boundary; therefore, future work should include direct process-energy measurements, scale-up validation, and application-specific evaluation of the produced biochars. Overall, the framework provides a reproducible basis for more defensible and application-oriented operating-window selection for lavender-residue biochar valorization.

Supplementary Information

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Additional file 1.

Additional file 2.

Additional file 3.

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Data availability

All data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable. This study involved no human participants or animal experiments.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this manuscript, the author(s) used ChatGPT (OpenAI) to improve language clarity and to refine the description and presentation of the modelling methodology (e.g., equations and calculation workflow). All analyses and numerical calculations were performed and verified by the authors, who reviewed and edited the text and take full responsibility for the content.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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